
The Importance of Effective Welfare Management in Reducing Poverty

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Abstract: The article analyzes the well-being of the population and the specific features of reducing poverty by ensuring it. The level of poverty is expressed in the production capabilities of the country and the lifestyle of the population, its manifestation as a social problem in almost all economic systems has been studied, and mechanisms for reducing it have been developed.

Key words: Poverty, social policy, social and financial policy of the state, state budget expenditures, social sector expenditures, social support of the population.

If we say that today's changes in Uzbekistan have started a new history of the country, we are telling the truth. Already, huge innovations taking place in our country in socio-economic, political and other spheres ensure the literal integration of our country with the world community. The population of any country is not the same in terms of its composition and it changes over time, therefore, the patterns of living of the population, the standard of living, its structural changes, etc. are studied taking into account specific conditions. . The demographic composition of families employed in agriculture is unique, the number of people per family is 7.1 on average. Taking the example of a certain region, according to the results of the research conducted in the rural areas of Kashkadarya region, 25.0% of family members living there participate in social production, and 7.0% are pensioners. 68.0% of them are unemployed, 42% of them are children under the age of 16. This indicates that it will be necessary to create a lot of jobs in the villages of the region in terms of the demographic situation.

The category of poverty appears when the population cannot independently meet the minimum consumption requirements. Currently, in many countries, minimum consumption requirements are set at different scales, and it should be noted that their components differ from each other. In general, the determination of minimum consumer spending and its assessment are set by governments in countries. International organizations have also developed indicators of a recommendatory nature. In this regard, determination of poverty is carried out as a mutually harmonious process. In our opinion, the approach to determination of poverty using the methods of the minimum consumption standard reflects the minimum line of ensuring the well-being of the people. gives seven. For this reason, two aspects of the approach to living well-being arise when defining poverty by dividing it into material and non-material factors. From this point of view, reducing poverty is important in ensuring the well-being of the population. we passed In addition to economic factors, non-economic factors are also formed in the creation of this category, which requires improvement of approaches to the assessment of poverty. For example, in many developed countries, among the indicators of ensuring the well-being of the population, the fact that the weekly load of working hours is reduced from 5 to 4 days has begun to be taken into account, which means that the methodology of assessing the well-being of the population is not dogmatic.

It should be noted that poverty reduction is the main factor in ensuring the well-being of the population even in the nominal measurement criteria. It focuses on narrowing the gap between

high and low-income population. This creates the phenomenon that the state should pay attention to the population with higher incomes when collecting taxes. However, in the implementation of this phenomenon, the problem of improving the tax policy arises. From this point of view, it is also important to implement measures aimed at reducing income inequality. Several indicators of the 17 goals of sustainable development of the United Nations in 2015-2030 include aspects related to ensuring the well-being of the population. reflects. Among them, the first goal is to reduce poverty, and several others are supposed to cover such factors as ending hunger, education, health and providing clean drinking water. In general, while the above-mentioned indicators have a special place in ensuring the well-being of the population, in this part of our research, we will implement an approach from the point of view of reducing poverty. In our opinion, it is appropriate to pay attention to aspects such as reducing the income of the population and its inequality, stabilizing the income of the population in the fiscal policy, while developing our approach to reducing poverty in ensuring the well-being of the population. Cambridge University Professor H. Dalton 1920- In his article published in 2011, he describes scientific approaches to the assessment of income inequality. In his opinion, from the point of view of economic well-being, he emphasizes the need to be based on income when determining inequality. It tries to prove that there is a high correlation between income and economic well-being. It is justified by the existence of a proportional relationship between income and economic well-being. Income is taken as the main criterion in his research. From the 70s of the last century, scientific approaches to economic inequality began to be developed. In particular, another professor of Cambridge University, A. Atkinson, tried to evaluate social welfare based on income in 1970 [3]. He suggests focusing on the distribution of personal income before and after taxes. He believes that social welfare is ensured with equal incomes. In ensuring income inequality, it is recommended to influence it through tax policy and use its redistribution function. Professor A. Einer and A. Haynes of the University of Illinois conduct research on income inequality in 1967 [4]. In their opinion, they positively assess the possibility of achieving a stable distribution of income with the help of taxes using a progressive rate. However, they show that if this progressive rate leads to a decrease in the enthusiasm of employees for work, a decrease in gross income will occur. In our opinion, scientific approaches to income inequality were first formed in the research aimed at ensuring the well-being of the population. The development of these trends had an impact on the emergence of the social state category. It is based on preliminary scientific conclusions that achieving equal distribution of income serves to ensure socio-economic well-being. In our opinion, by the 21st century, as a result of the development of information technologies and the development of approaches to the category of poverty, income inequality has the status of a full indicator. shows that it may not. Therefore, there is a need to improve the social protection programs of the state along with the factors that lead to income inequality in reducing the category of poverty.

The socio-economic essence of determining the level of poverty. The purpose of determining and analyzing the poverty indicator is to support the lifestyle of the vulnerable and vulnerable people in each country through targeted programs. In this regard, international organizations, including the UN, define the poverty line as the income needed for basic goods and services. The overall welfare index of each country depends on the criteria of the poverty level and the social policies implemented to reduce it. In world practice, three concepts of poverty calculation are widely used: absolute, relative and subjective. These concepts do not negate each other, on the contrary, they complement each other.

The human development index is defined as an indicator that evaluates the share of gross national income per capita, the literacy level of the population, and the longevity of the population. occupies the rins. The human development index takes into account 3 main factors - living a long and healthy life, getting an education and a decent standard of living. Standard of living nominal and real average salary level, minimum amount of pension and benefit, average and real amount of pension, average and real per capita income stratification indicators, minimum amount of marriage, and marriage is determined by the weight of the population with the lowest income. The

level of education includes three main indicators in the country's education system: the duration of the academic year, the expected duration of education, the average duration of education, and these indicators have a significant impact on the standard of living of the population. 'secret shows. Mechanisms of poverty reduction are considered as an economic tool of the macroeconomic system, and specific measures and measures are implemented in order to achieve the goal. It represents the development of the criteria and assessment methodology for determining the level of poverty, the normative basis of the minimum standards of social security, and the effective coordination of the activities of state administration bodies and non-governmental non-profit organizations for poverty reduction. The mechanism identifies the factors that cause poverty and income inequality and consists of a set of methods of systematic work to achieve the goals of sustainable development.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 28 yanvar, PF-60-son 2022 — 2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida Farmoni. Qonunchilik ma‘lumotlari milliy bazasi, 29.01.2022 y., 06/22/60/0082-son).
2. Madrahimov U.A. O‘zbekistonda barqaror iqtisodiy o‘shish sifatini oshirish yo‘llari. I.f.d.avtoreferati. Toshkent. 2017 y. - 17 b.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M. Mirziyoyevning 2020 yil 24 yanvardagi Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. "Xalq so‘zi" gazetasi, 2020 yil 25 yanvar, № 19 (7521)
4. Руководство по измерению бедности. ЕЭК, ООН, Нью-Йорк-Женева, 2017 г. с.4.
5. Jumayev N. Koronavirus ortidagi iqtisodiy muammolar, kambag'allik, oshayotgan tashqi qarz va YeOII. 16.04.2020.
6. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Milliy taraqqiyot yo‘limizni qatiyat bilan davom ettirib, yangi bosqichga ko‘taramiz. - Toshkent: "O‘zbekiston" NMIU, 2017. - 156 b.
7. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M. Mirziyoyevning 2020 yil 24 yanvardagi Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. "Xalq so‘zi" gazetasi, 2020 yil 25 yanvar, № 19 (7521).
8. Mustafaqulov Sh. Murodullayev N. va boshqalar.O‘zbekistonda kambag'allikni aniqlash va qisqartirish davlat siyosati darajasida. "Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar" Ilmiy elektron jurnali. 80 b №1, yanvar-fevral, 2020 yil. <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>